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Title

**MEASURING THE WOMEN'S INVOLVEMENT IN
PURCHASE MAKING DECISIONS**

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ABSTRACT:

The purpose of this paper is to measure the relationship between demographic & geographic variables of women and their involvement in purchase making decisions of family and it also measures the level of involvement of women in these decisions. Data were collected through self-administered questionnaire. The sample consists of 200 women accessed through personal survey from shopping malls, multiplexes, and academic institutions when they visited these on week days. Chi Square test of independence and Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test analysis has been carried out. Result reveals a significant relationship between various demographic (age, education, working nature, occupation, marital status, type and size of family) and geographic (residing area) variables of women and their involvement in purchase making decisions of family except only one variable: income. Result also that reveals a high degree of involvement of women in purchase making decisions of the family has been found.

Keywords: Purchase Making Decisions, Demographic and Geographic Variables, Women, Pune.

INTRODUCTION:

Women are integral part of our society. In India, where population of women alone is more than the total population of many countries even though a few years ago, Indian society was male dominated while women were involved in only managing home; fulfilling the need of family members in terms of tasty and healthy food, neat and clean clothes etc. The last decade has witnessed a substantial change in the role of women in Indian society. The dependence of Indian economy is shifting towards activities unrelated to physical strength. Due to this shift, women are now capable of performing most economic task. Indian societies are also experiencing a change in cultural norms and ideas related to men's and women's task. Traditional role of men and women in society has been merged. Women are increasingly performing task traditionally assigned to men and vice versa. In addition, women are also getting greater autonomy, thereby no longer being dependent upon men for economic and social support and recognition. Due to these changes, women's roles have a major impact upon performance of task with in society.

Major shift in societal role shows a reflection in family purchase making decisions. Now scenario has been changed due to increase in literacy rate and working women forces. Therefore role of women has been also changed in the family. Now women not only manage the home successfully but also take part in purchase making decisions of family. This study is to measure the relationship between demographic & geographic variables of women and their involvement in purchase making decisions of family and it also examine the level of involvement of women in these decisions. Before inhabiting on the hypothesis of the research, a brief literature has been covered for review.

LITRATURE REVIEW:

Green and Cunningham (1975) compared family decision-making patterns under different conditions of female role perception. Their findings suggest differences between contemporary and traditional families, particularly within age and income categories. Purchasing involvement is related to sex, education, income, and stage of the family life cycle (Slama and Tashchian, 1985).

William J. Qualls (1987) examined the impact of sex role orientation on the outcome of a family home purchase decisions and found a relatively strong relationship between sex role orientation and the degree of house hold influence, preference agreement mode of conflict resolution, and decision outcome. Furthermore, it is also found that household decision behavior is better explained in the context of a theoretical network of systematic house hold relationship rather than through a series of bivariate family relationship.

Cynthia Webster (1994) revealed a significant positive relationship between ethnic identification and husband dominance in decision making. However, because ethnic identification and product class interact with role specialization and relative influence in decision making, generalizations cannot be made about Hispanic marital roles in the decision-making process. Furthermore, the effect of ethnic identification on marital roles in decision making interacts with the phase of purchase decision process.

Kang and Kim (1998) examined the decision-making patterns for purchasing social clothes of three major Asian American consumer groups (Chinese, Japanese, and Korean). Results showed that the three groups display distinct reference group influence, media influence, and store attribute importance and that these patterns differ depending on the level of acculturation. The findings also suggested implications for various marketing and advertising strategies aimed at the three Asian American consumer markets.

Customer purchase decisions are affected by customer satisfaction (Gerpott *et al.*, 2001). A significant relationship is found between the involvement and brand loyalty in grocery market, by Knox and Walker, (2003). Singh and Kaur (2006) studied children's role in purchase decisions of the family and found that children in India have not much purchasing power in comparison of western counterpart. Still children in India not only influence market in terms of parental decisions but also represent themselves as future customers. Significant influences of demographic variables like age, occupation, family income are noticed in case of selection of products (Parmar and Gupta, 2007).

Rajesh Sud, (2007) found that the family structure in India has changed considerably in the last two decades. Nuclear families are replacing joint family. There is an increase in literacy rate of women and working women forces. Now parent centered families has been changed in child centered families. Hence the role of children in family decision making is increasing. Kotwal *et al.* (2008) pointed out that adolescent girls, influence of friends, and peers are the main cause for purchasing clothing items. Pathak and Tripathi (2009) argued that Indian customers have become more sensitive to quality, customer services and status.

The review of literature discussed above provides a deep insight of the work done by experts and researchers on some aspects of purchase decisions. However, lots of studies have been done to analyze women's role in family purchase decisions but in foreign context. Therefore present study was taken in Indian context.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS:

H₀1: There is no significant relationship between demographic variables of women and their involvement in purchase making decisions of family.

H0₂: There is no significant relationship between geographic variables of women and their involvement in purchase making decisions of family.

H0₃: There is no significant involvement of women in purchase making decisions of family.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Data Source

The study was based on both primary and secondary data. Secondary data was accumulated from books, journals, websites and other published sources available and it helped to formulate hypothesis, questionnaire, and review of literature. Utilizing the information from the secondary data, a structured questionnaire was prepared for women to accumulate the primary data, comprising open and closed ended questions. This questionnaire was tested by conducting a pilot study of randomly selected few women respondents. Utilizing the insight from pilot study, questionnaire was modified for the final study. Both Descriptive and exploratory research were used in compiling this study. While exploratory research helped in developing the hypothesis through the analysis of secondary data, descriptive research was used in order to complete this whole study. Survey method was employed to carry out this study through printed questionnaires by personal interview technique. Nominal and Ordinal scales are utilized to take the response of respondents. Location of Research was Pune city of Maharashtra state. Simple percentage method has been used to analyze the demographic and geographic variables of respondents. Chi Square Test of Independence is applied to find out relationship between demographic and geographic variables of women and their involvement in purchase making decisions of family. Kolmogorov-Smirnov One Sample test has been applied to know degree of involvement of women in purchase making decisions of family. Cross tabulation has been utilized to represent the responses of respondents.

Sampling Plan

Women respondents were selected on random basis from shopping malls, multiplexes, and academic institutions when they visited these on week days. The questionnaires were distributed

simultaneously among 200 respondents during July-August 2011. Survey was done in all seven days. For the purpose of this survey, Random Sampling of Probability Sampling Technique has been employed as it gives every unit of the population a known and non-zero probability of being selected.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION:

A) Relationship between Demographic Variables of Women and their Involvement in Purchase Making Decisions of the Family

1) Age Group and Involvement in Purchase Making Decisions

Table 1 delineates that majority of women who belonged to age group 36-45 years (14%) had high involvement, majority of them who belonged to age group of 18-25 years (11.5%) had medium involvement and majority of them who belonged to age group of below 18 years and 46-55 years (3.5%) had low involvement. Table 1 also delineates chi square calculated is 54.191 at 5% of level of significance and 10 degree of freedom which is much greater than tabulated value i.e. 18.307. Therefore hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between age group of women and their involvement in purchase making decisions of family is rejected.

**Table 1: Cross tabulation of age group
of women and their involvement in purchase making decisions**

Age (Years)	High		Medium		Low		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
< 18	1	0.5	4	2.0	7	3.5	12	6
18-25	21	10.5	23	11.5	3	1.5	47	23.5
26-35	27	13.5	12	6.0	1	0.5	40	20
36-45	28	14.0	13	6.5	2	1.0	43	21

46-55	15	7.5	13	6.5	7	3.5	35	17.5
> 55	3	1.5	16	8.0	4	2.0	23	11.5
Total	95	47.5	81	40.5	24	12.0	200	100
Chi Square Calculated								
df		Level of significance			Chi Square Tabulated			
54.191		10		5%		18.307		

2) Education and Involvement in Purchase Making Decisions

Table 2 depicts that majority of women who were postgraduate (28%) had high involvement, majority of them who were graduate (11.5%) had medium involvement and majority of them whose education was 10th to 12th standard (5.5%) had low involvement. Table 2 also depicts chi square calculated is 63.06 at 5% of level of significance and 8 degree of freedom which is much greater than tabulated value i.e. 15.507. Therefore hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between education of women and their involvement in purchase making decisions of family is rejected.

Table 2: Cross tabulation of education of women and their involvement in purchase making decisions

Education	High		Medium		Low		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Illiterate	3	1.5	8	4.0	2	1.0	13	6.5
< 10th	4	2.0	19	9.5	7	3.5	30	15
10th-12th	8	4.0	15	7.5	11	5.5	34	17
Graduation	24	12.0	23	11.5	4	2.0	51	25.5

Post Graduation	56	28.0	16	8.0	0	0.0	72	36
Total	95	47.5	81	40.5	24	12	200	100
Chi Square Calculated								
Chi Square Calculated		df	Level of significance		Chi Square Tabulated			
63.06		8	5%		15.507			

3) Working Nature and Involvement in Purchase Making Decisions

Table 3 presents that majority of women who were working (26%) had high involvement, majority of them who were working (22%) had medium involvement and majority of them who were not working (9%) had low involvement. Table 3 also presents chi square calculated is 7.38 at 5% of level of significance and 2 degree of freedom which is greater than tabulated value i.e. 5.991. Therefore hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between working nature of women and their involvement in purchase making decisions of family is rejected.

Working Nature	High		Medium		Low		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Yes	52	26	44	22	6	3	102	51
No	43	21.5	37	18.5	18	9	98	49
Total	95	47.5	81	40.5	24	12	200	100
Chi Square								
Chi Square		df	Level of significance		Chi Square			

Calculated			Tabulated
7.38	2	5%	5.991

4) Occupation and Involvement in Purchase Making Decisions

Table 4 shows that majority of women who were salaried (18.5%) had high involvement, majority of them who were house wife (14.5%) had medium involvement and majority of them who were students (4%) had low involvement. Table 4 also shows chi square calculated is 31.067 at 5% of level of significance and 8 degree of freedom which is greater than tabulated value i.e. 15.987. Therefore hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between occupation status of women and their involvement in purchase making decisions is rejected.

Table 4: Cross tabulation of occupation status of women and their involvement in purchase making decisions								
Occupation	High		Medium		Low		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Students	11	5.5	18	9	8	4	37	18.5
Salaried	37	18.5	15	7.5	4	2	56	28
Own Business	29	14.5	14	7	3	1.5	46	23
House Wife	18	9	29	14.5	6	3	53	26.5
Others	0	0	5	2.5	3	1.5	8	4
Total	95	47.5	81	40.5	24	12	200	100
Chi Square Calculated	df		Level of significance			Chi Square Tabulated		

31.067	8	5%	15.987
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5) Marital Status and Involvement in Purchase Making Decisions

Table 5 explains that majority of women who were married (36%) had high involvement, majority of them who were married (24.5%) had medium involvement and majority of them who were married (7.5%) had low involvement. Table 5 also explains chi square calculated is 12.798 at 5% of level of significance and 2 degree of freedom, which is much greater than tabulated value i.e. 5.991. Therefore hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between marital status of women and their involvement in purchase making decisions of family is rejected.

Marital Status	High		Medium		Low		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Single	23	11.5	32	16	9	4.5	84	42
Married	72	36	49	24.5	15	7.5	116	58
Total	95	47.5	81	40.5	24	12	200	100
Chi Square Calculated		df	Level of significance			Chi Square Tabulated		
12.798		2	5%			5.991		

6) Income and Involvement in Purchase Making Decisions

Table 6 describes that majority of women whose monthly income was 21000-30000 (8%) had high involvement, majority of them whose monthly income was 5000-10000 (4.5%) had medium involvement and majority of them whose monthly income was below 5000 (2%) had low

involvement. Table 6 also describes delineates chi square calculated is 7.179 at 5% of level of significance and 10 degree of freedom which is much less than tabulated value i.e. 18.307. Therefore hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between income of women and their involvement in purchase making decisions of family is accepted.

Income (Monthly)	High		Medium		Low		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
< 5000	8	4	7	3.5	4	2	19	9.5
5000-10000	12	6	9	4.5	3	1.5	24	12
11000-15000	9	4.5	6	3	2	1	17	8.5
16000-20000	5	2.5	4	2	2	1	11	5.5
21000-30000	16	8	5	2.5	1	0.5	22	11
> 30000	6	3	3	1.5	0	0	9	4.5
Total	56	28	34	17	12	6	102	51
Chi Square Calculated	df		Level of significance			Chi Square Tabulated		
7.179	10		5%			18.307		

7) Type of Family and Involvement in Purchase Making Decisions

Table 7 delineates that majority of women who belonged to nuclear family (38%) had high involvement, majority of them who belonged to nuclear family (24.5%) had medium involvement and majority of them who belonged to nuclear family (8%) had low involvement. Table 7 delineates chi square calculated is 8.191 at 5% of level of significance and 2 degree of freedom which is greater than tabulated value i.e. 5.991. Therefore hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between family type of women and their involvement in purchase making decisions of family is rejected.

Family Type	High		Medium		Low		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Nuclear	76	38	49	24.5	16	8	141	70.5
Joint	19	9.5	32	16	8	4	59	29.5
Total	95	47.5	81	40.5	24	12	200	100
Chi Square Calculated	df		Level of significance			Chi Square Tabulated		
8.191	2		5%			5.991		

8) Size of Family and Involvement in Purchase Making Decisions

Table 8 depicts that majority of women who belonged to family of size 4-5 members (19.5%) had high involvement, majority of them who belonged to family of size 4-5 and 6-7 members (16%) had medium involvement and majority of them who belonged to family of size 4- 5 (6%) had low involvement. Table 8 also depicts chi square calculated is 21.141 at 5% of level of significance and 6 degree of freedom which is much greater than tabulated value i.e. 12.592.

Therefore hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between family size of women and their involvement in purchase making decisions of family is rejected.

Table 8: Cross tabulation of family size of women and their involvement in purchase making decisions

Family Size	High		Medium		Low		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
2 to 3	28	14	8	8	2	1	38	19
4 to 5	39	19.5	32	16	12	6	83	41.5
6 to 7	16	8	32	16	5	2.5	53	26.5
> 7	12	6	9	4.5	5	2.5	26	13
Total	95	47.5	81	40.5	24	12	200	100
Chi Square Calculated		df	Level of significance			Chi Square Tabulated		
21.141		6	5%			12.592		

B) Relationship between Geographic Variables of Women and Their Involvement in Purchase Making Decisions of the Family

9) Residing Area and Involvement in Purchase Making Decisions

Table 9 shows that majority of women who resided in urban area (34%) had high involvement, majority of them who resided in urban area (25.5%) had medium involvement and majority of them who resided in rural area (9.5%) had low involvement. Table 2.2 delineates chi square

calculated is 20.995 at 5% of level of significance and 2 degree of freedom which is much greater than tabulated value i.e. 5.991. Therefore hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between residing area of women and their involvement in purchase making decisions of family is rejected.

Area	High		Medium		Low		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Urban	68	34.0	51	25.5	5	2.5	124	62
Rural	27	13.5	30	15.0	19	9.5	76	38
Total	95	47.5	81	40.5	24	12.0	200	100
Chi Square Calculated		df	Level of significance		Chi Square Tabulated			
20.995		2	5%		5.991			

C) Level of involvement of women in purchase making decisions of the family

To analyze the level of involvement of women in making purchase decisions of family, responses has been taken on ordinal scale ranging from high involvement to low involvement. To find out the degree of involvement between a set of value observed and values specified by the null hypothesis, Kolmogorov-Smirnov One Sample Test has been applied. Calculated Kolmogorov-Smirnov D Value is 0.22. The critical value of D at an alpha of 5% is 0.096. As the calculated D exceeds the critical value of 0.096, the null hypothesis that there is no significant involvement of women in purchase making decisions of family is rejected.

CONCLUSION:

Study states a significant relationship between various demographic (Age group, Education status, Occupation status, Marital Status, Type and size of family) and geographic (Residing area) variables of women and their involvement in purchase making decisions of family except only one variable: income. Study depicts a high degree of involvement of women in purchase making decisions of the family. Results show that women who belonged to age group 26-55 years, well educated, working with salary, contributing a good amount to household income had high involvement in purchase making decisions of the family. Women who were working had high involvement in purchase making decisions of the family in comparison to no working women. Women who were married had also high involvement in purchase making decisions of the family in comparison to unmarried women. Women who belonged to nuclear family and resided in urban area had high involvement. I also noticed an increase in literacy level and working women population. Now women are contributing good amount to the house hold income.

RESEARCH LIMITATIONS & IMPLICATIONS:

Study was limited to a few women selected on random basis. Due to short of time and resources study was confined to only a selected region of Pune district. This study furnishes information about women's demographic and geographic variables and relationship between various demographic and geographic variables of women and their involvement in purchase making decisions of the family.

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